

Circular Agronomics: producing high-quality organic fertilizers from digestates in an agro-industrial biogas plant

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Abstract:

Six high-value organic fertilizers (OF) will be produced in a combined process based on anaerobic digestion of pig manure with agro-industrial organic wastes, followed by an efficient solid-liquid separation (centrifuge) and solar drying. The digestate concentrates will be submitted to a stripping treatment to produce two liquid streams, one of them enriched in N and available for fertilization. The mass (C, N, P, K) and energy balances will be performed, including gaseous emission monitoring, along the production of different OFs. Among physico-chemical parameters, the agronomical potential of such products will be tested in field crop rotations, as well as horticultural crops. The overall process of OFs production will be characterized, based on compiled data from balances, emissions and products' yield and characteristics. Finally, once the OFs production process will be well defined, these data will feed a Life Cycle Analysis assessment. This digestate valorization process is one of the case studies of the European project 'Circular Agronomics'.

Keywords: organic fertilizers, anaerobic digestion, solar drying.

Session: Post-treatments anaerobic effluents/digestates.

Introduction

Catalonia represents a typical Mediterranean biogeographic region, with mild winters and warm summers and receives many hours of sunshine, free of clouds. Generally, soil C content is low, being a challenge for soil conservation. In the previous decades, agriculture has been oriented towards livestock production, and nowadays represents more than 65 % of the total farming activity (over 80 % in some regions). Moreover, Catalonia has a high farming intensity in relation to the overall agricultural land and livestock is concentrated in specific areas, resulting in high nitrate levels in groundwater, surplus of nutrients in the soil and risk of emissions to the atmosphere (Durán et al., 2017).

Many studies have been carried out on the evaluation of the detrimental effects of modern agricultural systems and the possible methods of reduction of the impact that could be implemented. In particular, nitrogen and phosphorus losses, including nitrogen leaching that contributes to eutrophication and ammonia emissions from livestock manure with negative effects in soils, forests and biodiversity.

In order to apply manure and other agro-industrial wastes as fertilizers, it is necessary to carry out innovative treatments to obtain well-formulated fertilizers, easier to store, transport, handle and apply, as well as by implementing technologies to extract nutrients from digestates and to significantly reduce GHG and nitrogen oxides emissions.

The aim of this work is to present a high-value organic fertilizers (OF) production process that valorize digestates from the anaerobic co-digestion of pig manure and agro-industrial organic wastes. With that purpose, innovative approach through solar drying and stripping applied to the solid and liquid fractions of digestates will be assessed at semi-industrial scale. Important aspects such emission monitoring and minimization strategies during the OFs

production, as well as the agronomical characterization of fertilizers, will be performed. The fertilizer potential will be tested in field crop rotations as well as horticultural crops, and soil characteristics will be monitored.

This research work is currently being carried out in the framework of the H2020 project 'Circular Agronomics'. The study is part of the Catalonia Case Study (Spain), one of the six case studies established around Europe, representing a variety of biogeographic scenarios and environmental challenges typical for the European agricultural sector (Spain, Germany, Austria, Italy, Netherlands and Czech Republic).

Materials and methods

The concentrated and centrate fractions of digestates from a biogas plant treating pig manure and agro-industrial organic wastes will be submitted to a specifically designed solar drying and stripping treatments, respectively. Two similar pilot-scale solar dryers are being designed and installed in order to operate them in parallel for 3 years; then, one of them will be modified to heat the incoming air, after heat exchange with combustion gases from the cogeneration engine. The stripping unit includes two columns (with air and sulfuric, respectively) able to remove ammonia from the digestate concentrates. The resulting N-rich stripping stream will be available for fertilization or fertigation, while the secondary liquid stream would be used in the drying process or for TS adjustment of fresh wastes previously to the anaerobic digestion. A key point of the process is the acidification of the solar dryer inflows, which avoid N emissions; in this sense, alternative acidification processes as CO₂ bubbling (or collected combustion gases from the cogeneration engine of the biogas plant) will be investigated to replace usual reagents (sulfuric acid).

The fertilizer potential (field and small scale tests) will be crucial to define which OF will be the best. As the objective of the process is to close both N and P cycles at farm level by producing this high-quality OF, therefore the process monitoring (including gaseous emissions), the raw and final products characterization and the energy consumption indexes will be crucial to perform the mass (C, N, P, K) and energy balances. Finally, once the best OF will be well defined, these data will feed a Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) assessment.

Results and Conclusions

Typical digestates have an average dry matter content of 8% wet weight which is expected to increase till 20% and 80% wet weight after centrifugation and solar drying, respectively. The removal efficiency of a stripping process depends on a number of operational parameters. As mentioned, the main parameters are pH and temperature, as they have a direct effect over ammonia speciation (NH₄⁺/NH₃), but other parameters such as the characteristics of the inflow stream should be also taken into account. In this regard, a distinct relationship between the inflow characteristics and removal efficiency has not yet been clearly established, but the content of organic matter is likely to be the most relevant parameter (Laureni et al., 2013).

Slurries with an initial low organic matter (< 10 gCOD L⁻¹) content led to higher N removal efficiencies (> 90%) when stripping was performed at 50 °C and pH was not modified. In contrast, nitrogen removal efficiency was limited to about 50% when organic matter concentrations were high, above 27 gCOD L⁻¹ (Laureni et al., 2013).

Six different OFs will be tested in agronomical assays. These products will result after drying 5 materials (acidified fresh wastes, acidified concentrated digestate fraction alone and mixed with stripping streams) and non-dried & non-acidified digestates. Figure 1 shows schematically the experimental procedure. The OFs from acidified digestates or concentrated fraction of digestates are expected to be the more stabilized fertilizers (red and yellow lines in Fig.1),

having the last a higher P content. In parallel, those OFs produced after including the N-rich stripping stream are expected to be more balance in N/P/K content. Finally, those OFs produced after mixing the concentrate fraction of digestate and the secondary liquid stripping stream are expected to ease the operational costs of the process. Acidification strategies will drastically reduce ammonia emissions during the drying process. Moreover, emissions will also be controlled by implementing biofiltration systems in each dryer. Mass and energy balances will determine how the nutrients are distributed among the different streams.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the experimental procedure. Colours: Green line, acidified-dried raw manure & co-substrates. Red line, acidified-dried digestate (red). Yellow line, acidified digestate solid fraction. Blue line, acidified digestate solid fraction & N-rich liquid stripping stream. Purple line, acidified digestate solid fraction & secondary liquid stripping stream. Brown line, non-acidified & non-dried digestate (or reference material in the agronomic tests).

As mid-term vision until 2030, an annual GHG emissions reduction of approximately 100 Mt-CO₂-eq year⁻¹ (reduction of 10-15% of direct GHG emissions in agriculture) in EU-28 is achievable based on the evolution of emission generation from agriculture till today, and the efficiency of the proposed practices and technologies. Out of this reduction, 75% will come by reducing the N₂O loss to the atmosphere (increased agronomic efficiency) and 25% by reducing the CH₄ losses (via measures in livestock farming) (Global Research Alliance on Agricultural Greenhouse Gases and the Sustainable Agriculture Initiative Platform, 2015). Additionally, approximately 7 Mt-CO₂-eq year⁻¹ will be reduced via the recovery approaches for N and P fertilizers (avoiding CO₂-intensive production of conventional fertilizers: -1.7 and -0.2 Mt year⁻¹ for N and P, respectively) (Schoumans et al., 2015). In this framework, the OFs production studied in this work is expect to increase by 20% the agronomic efficiency, in terms of nutrient usage in conventional farming compared to nowadays, and specifically by 15-30% and 15-40% for N and P, respectively. Regarding the avoided emissions, it is expected summing up to a total potential avoided emission of approximately 2 and 0.2 Mt year⁻¹ for N and P, respectively.

For areas with low carbon stocks in soil (e.g. Catalonia soils has an average content <20 gC kg-soil⁻¹ (Jones et al., 2012), a realistic target is to increase C stocks by 10% until 2030

(significant higher growth rate than 4%) (4 per 1000 initiative). This challenge is hampered by simultaneous N and P surplus in soils, limiting direct recycling of available bio-solids. Solutions addressed in the 'Circular Agronomics' project will ensure that organic carbon can be recycled to soil without generating potentially negative effects by high concentrations of nutrients in manure.

The secondary goal after increasing the agronomic efficiency for N and P, in combination with realignment of nutrient inputs, is a reduced release of agricultural emissions (especially nitrate but also phosphate) to water bodies. Those technologies aiming for N-depletion of bio-solids and removal of inorganic ammonium (e.g. from manure) are highlighted in this context. For example, the N-depleted manure will be recycled on arable land, whereby organic-bounded N will be mineralizing slowly during vegetation period. The inorganic ammonia, responsible for high nitrate leaching, will be recovered as fertilizer, which is transportable or can be applied when an actual N-demand by plants exists. This procedure will reduce nitrate emissions to receiving water bodies by 50% in regions with high nitrogen surplus and by 10-15% as European average (Buckwell and Nadeu (2016)).

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